

D5.1 (T5.1): Interactive dashboard showing the extent of skill waste across European Union Member States

Deliverable factsheet			
Title and number	Interactive dashboard showing the extent of skill waste across EUMS.		
Work Package and task:	WP5, task 5.1		
Submission date	25/06/2025 (following the upload to the project website)		
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Reviewers	Oloba Oluwajoba (The NEST), Ksenija Ivanović (Radboud University)		
Access to the database	The interactive dashboard D5.1 is available via the following link: https://gs4s.eu/dashboard/		
Dissemination level	PU (Public)		
Deliverable type	Interactive dashboard		
Version log			
Issue Date	Version n°	Author/reviewer	Change
24/09/2024	v0.1	All authors	Authors submitted to reviewers the database upon which the interactive dashboard is built, as well as an explanatory note (see in continuation).
30/09/2024	v0.2	Oloba Oluwajoba, Ksenija Ivanović	Reviewers had no suggestions or further comments.
30/09/2024	v0.3	All authors	The interactive dashboard is live and ready for submission.
15/06/2025	v.04	All authors	The interactive dashboard has been reviewed upon feedback by the external reviewers.
25/06/2025	v.05	Coordinators	The coordinators resubmit the deliverable, following its upload to the project website.

The interactive dashboard (D5.1, T5.1) is a deliverable of the Horizon Europe project ‘Global Strategy for Skills, Migration and Development. As stated in the ‘deliverable factsheet’ above, the database is available at the following link: <https://gs4s.eu/dashboard/>. An analysis of methodology and findings is presented in the companion working paper D7.3 in T5.1, submitted on September 30th, 2024.

